

(Reviewers:1/2/3) Generalization of Paper and Fully-unstructured Mesh

We provide some examples from large group of applications where our explorations in this paper should be applicable as follows.

- Regional mantle convection
(https://www.dealii.org/current/doxygen/deal.II/step_53.html)
- Global mantle convection (full Earth)
(<https://academic.oup.com/gji/article/192/3/889/809594>)
- Earthquake hazard mitigation (mesh shown on p. 49)
(<https://geodynamics.org/cig/news/research-highlights/november-2020/>)
- Cancer treatment
(<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40430-020-02760-1>)
- Modeling of laser welding
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0017931017306919>)
- Computer graphics
(<https://developer.nvidia.com/gpugems/gpugems2/part-v-image-oriented-computing/chapter-37-octree-textures-gpu>)
- Immerso-geometric analysis (fluid dynamics)
(https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0045793020303340?dgcid=rss_sd_all)
- Flow in porous media (p. 18)
(<https://www.oden.utexas.edu/media/reports/2018/1803.pdf>)
- Steady flow solvers (Nek5000)
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0045793019303111>)